

The Effect of Work Discipline and Work Competence on Service Performance Mediated by Work Motivation

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ABSTRACT: This research is motivated by the importance of improving the quality of public services, which is strongly influenced by the behavior and capabilities of civil servants. This study aims to examine the influence of work discipline and work competence on service performance, with work motivation as a mediating variable, at the Mojokerto City Civil Service Police Unit, East Java, Indonesia. This study used an explanatory research approach with a cross-sectional design. The population of this study was 73 employees. The sample size was determined using a saturated sampling technique, where the entire population was sampled. The results indicate that work discipline and work competence have a positive and significant effect on work motivation, and that work motivation has a significant effect on service performance. Furthermore, work motivation has been shown to mediate the relationship between work discipline and work competence on service performance. This finding confirms that improving employee discipline and competence will lead to higher motivation, thus positively impacting the quality of public services.

KEYWORDS: Work discipline; Work competence; Work motivation and Service performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Every organization, whether in the public or private sector, has the primary goal of achieving optimal performance, particularly in providing quality services to the public. In the context of public service organizations, service performance is a crucial indicator of an institution's success in meeting public needs and expectations. Quality service is measured not only by speed and accuracy, but also by the attitude, responsibility, and professionalism of staff in carrying out their duties (Hardiyansyah, 2020). Therefore, improving service performance requires synergy between various internal factors, including work discipline, work competence, and work motivation (Rivai & Sagala, 2018; Wibowo, 2022).

Work discipline is a fundamental factor determining the quality of human resources within an organization. Discipline reflects the level of employee compliance, responsibility, and awareness of established work rules and standards. Employees with high levels of discipline tend to arrive on time, complete tasks according to procedures, and maintain a good work ethic. Conversely, low work discipline will result in decreased productivity and service quality. According to Rivai (2018), work discipline is a form of mental and character training that fosters self-control and awareness of compliance with organizational regulations. Recent research by Rahmawati and Nugroho (2021) shows that work discipline positively influences public service performance because it fosters a responsible and consistent work culture. In the context of public services, discipline is the primary foundation for building public trust in government institutions (Suharto, 2022).

In addition to discipline, work competence is also a crucial factor influencing service performance. Competence encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to carry out tasks effectively. Competent employees are able to adapt to change, solve problems appropriately, and provide services responsive to public needs. Spencer and Spencer (1993) emphasized that work competence is not only related to technical abilities but also involves behavioral dimensions that determine an individual's effectiveness at work. In the context of public bureaucracy, improving employee competence is part of human resource reform to create a professional government oriented toward excellent service (Baharuddin, 2020; Siregar & Lubis, 2023). Wibowo's (2020) findings also confirm that employees with high competence tend to provide faster, more accurate, and more satisfying services to the public.

However, high discipline and competence do not necessarily automatically result in optimal service performance without the support of work motivation. Motivation is an internal force that drives individuals to act to achieve organizational goals. Motivated employees have the enthusiasm to work beyond targets, are proactive, and are committed to achieving results. Herzberg (1959), in his two-factor theory, emphasized that work motivation is influenced by intrinsic factors such as achievement, recognition, and

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responsibility. In the context of public service, work motivation can bridge the gap between individual abilities and actual performance in the field (Handoko, 2021). When work motivation increases, employee discipline and competence are more easily realized in the form of quality service performance (Prabowo & Astuti, 2023).

Various studies have consistently demonstrated a positive relationship between work discipline, competence, and employee performance. Highly disciplined employees tend to comply with organizational rules, complete tasks on time, and maintain consistent productivity. Meanwhile, competence, reflected in knowledge, skills, and attitudes, improves work quality and problem-solving abilities. Together, disciplined and competent employees contribute significantly to achieving organizational goals and improving overall performance effectiveness (Robbins & Judge, 2019; Armstrong, 2020; Mangkunegara, 2017; Rivai & Sagala, 2019; Mathis & Jackson, 2020). Rahmawati and Nugroho (2021) also revealed that employees with higher levels of discipline tend to demonstrate better time management, consistency, and commitment, which positively impact their service delivery. Furthermore, Siregar and Lubis (2023) found that employee competence significantly improves work quality and organizational responsiveness, particularly in the digital era of public administration. Furthermore, research by Suharyono, Mulyadi, and Riani (2022) shows that work motivation acts as a mediating variable, strengthening the influence of discipline and competence on employee performance in the government sector. This conclusion aligns with the research findings of Prabowo and Astuti (2023), which found that motivated employees tend to translate their competence and discipline into higher performance, particularly in public service institutions. Similarly, Yuliani and Hasan (2023) emphasize that motivation acts as a bridge between individual abilities and actual performance, ensuring that employee potential is effectively transformed into productive behavior. Handoko's (2024) more recent findings emphasize that the interaction between competence, discipline, and motivation is crucial in improving the quality and accountability of public service delivery. This means that even if employees possess high competence and discipline, without strong work motivation, service performance will not reach optimal levels (Baharuddin, 2024; KemenPANRB, 2024). Thus, motivation acts as an essential internal driver that activates employee capabilities and discipline, leading to improved performance and sustained service excellence in public sector organizations.

This phenomenon is also evident in various government agencies in Indonesia, where a mismatch between individual potential and resulting service performance persists. Many employees possess adequate capabilities but lack motivation due to factors such as the work environment, leadership, or ineffective reward systems (Sutrisno, 2021). As a result, the quality of public services is often inconsistent and does not fully meet public expectations (Yuliani & Hasan, 2023). Therefore, it is important to examine the role of work motivation as a mediating variable in strengthening the influence of discipline and competence on service performance.

This research is relevant and significant because it offers a comprehensive understanding of the interaction between three critical factors in human resource management: work discipline, work competence, and work motivation. By understanding the relationship between these three, public organizations can design more effective employee development strategies, for example through competency training, disciplinary enforcement, and the provision of incentives and rewards that can increase motivation. The results of this study are expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of human resource management science, as well as serve as an empirical basis for policy makers in efforts to improve the performance of professional, responsive, and public satisfaction-oriented public services (KemenPANRB, 2024; Robbins & Judge, 2019; Armstrong & Taylor, 2020).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

Service Performance

Service performance is one of the main indicators of organizational success, particularly in the public sector, which is oriented toward public satisfaction. This term refers to the level of effectiveness and efficiency of employees or agencies in providing services according to established standards (Lupiyoadi, 2018). Service performance is measured not only by the final result, but also by the service delivery process, which includes speed, accuracy, friendliness, and the quality of interactions between service providers and recipients (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988).

According to Sedarmayanti (2019), service performance reflects the extent to which employees are able to carry out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities and targets set by the organization. In the context of public services, this is closely related to public perception of the quality of government services. Fast, transparent, and responsive service will increase public trust, while slow and complicated service can damage the institution's image (Dwiyanto, 2018).

Factors influencing service performance include work discipline, employee competence, motivation, leadership, and organizational culture (Mangkunegara, 2020). Employees with high competence and strong motivation tend to provide quality service (Robbins & Judge, 2019). Furthermore, management system support and the use of information technology also play a crucial role in increasing the efficiency of service processes (Indrajit, 2020).

In the digital era, organizations are required to develop technology-based service innovations to meet increasingly high public expectations (Setiawan & Nugroho, 2021). Therefore, improving service performance is not only an individual responsibility but also requires comprehensive organizational transformation. Optimal service performance will ultimately create public satisfaction, strengthen the institution's legitimacy, and encourage good governance (Osborne, Radnor, & Nasi, 2013).

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Work Discipline

Work discipline is a crucial variable in human resource management, playing a significant role in determining an organization's effectiveness and productivity. Work discipline is defined as employees' awareness and willingness to comply with the regulations, norms, and standards established by the organization in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Discipline reflects an employee's level of commitment to organizational values and is a key indicator of a strong work ethic (Hasibuan, 2019). According to Rivai (2018), good work discipline is reflected in punctuality, responsibility for work, adherence to procedures, and consistency in carrying out tasks without close supervision.

Highly disciplined employees tend to exhibit positive work behaviors, such as completing work on time, maintaining quality work results, and respecting organizational rules and hierarchy. Conversely, low discipline can lead to various problems, such as decreased productivity, increased absenteeism, and a decline in overall work morale (Mangkunegara, 2017). Therefore, implementing an effective disciplinary system is an integral part of efforts to improve individual and organizational performance (Robbins & Judge, 2019).

Organizations can foster work discipline through fair policies, clear communication, and the proportional administration of sanctions and rewards. Furthermore, firm leadership and exemplary leadership from superiors also play a crucial role in fostering a culture of discipline in the workplace (Siagian, 2016). Thus, work discipline is not only a formal obligation, but also a manifestation of employee responsibility, dedication and integrity in achieving organizational goals optimally.

Work Competence

Work competence is a fundamental factor determining the quality and performance of individuals within an organization. This concept refers to a person's ability to perform tasks or work effectively based on their knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Spencer & Spencer, 1993; Armstrong, 2014). According to Wibowo (2020), competence reflects a combination of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects that enable employees to achieve the work standards expected by the organization. In other words, competence is not only about technical abilities but also encompasses values, motivation, and work behaviors that support productivity (Boyatzis, 2018).

In the context of public organizations, work competence plays a crucial role in improving service quality. Competent employees are better able to understand procedures, make informed decisions, and adapt to the dynamics of changing work environments (Sutrisno, 2019; Mangkunegara, 2017). Furthermore, competence also influences motivation and job satisfaction, as individuals who feel competent tend to have high self-confidence and commitment to their work (Robbins & Judge, 2017; Luthans, 2015).

Empirical research shows that work competence contributes significantly to improving individual and organizational performance. According to Suharyono, Mulyadi, and Riani (2022), technical, managerial, and social competence have a positive influence on the work effectiveness of public sector employees. Meanwhile, Rivai and Sagala (2020) emphasized that increasing competence through training and human resource development has been proven to improve public service performance sustainably. Therefore, work competence is a key foundation in creating superior human resources with integrity and adaptability to the challenges of modern organizations (Sedarmayanti, 2019; Werther & Davis, 2016).

Work Motivation

Work motivation is a crucial factor influencing employee effectiveness and productivity within an organization. The concept of work motivation refers to the internal and external drives that drive individuals to behave and work in accordance with organizational goals (Robbins & Judge, 2019). Motivation is a psychological force that directs, maintains, and determines the intensity of an individual's work behavior. Therefore, work motivation is not only related to individual needs but also to the extent to which the organization is able to create conditions that support satisfaction and optimal performance.

According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory (1943), human motivation arises from efforts to fulfill basic needs to the need for self-actualization. In the work context, employees will be motivated to perform well if physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization needs are met. Meanwhile, Herzberg (1968) distinguished between motivating factors that increase job satisfaction, such as achievement and recognition, and hygiene factors, such as pay and working conditions, that prevent dissatisfaction. Both theories emphasize the importance of a balance between fulfilling personal needs and a conducive work environment.

Furthermore, Vroom's (1964) expectancy theory emphasizes that individuals will be motivated to work hard if they believe their efforts will result in good performance and valuable rewards. In the context of public and educational organizations, work motivation plays a crucial role in increasing employee dedication, loyalty, and responsibility towards their assigned tasks (Wibowo, 2020).

Thus, work motivation not only serves as a driver of work behavior but also as a determining factor in organizational success in achieving its strategic goals. Organizations that are able to understand and manage employee work motivation will create a productive, harmonious, and high-performance work environment (Armstrong, 2014).

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The Role of Work Motivation as a Mediating Variable in the Effect of Work Discipline and Work Competence on Service Performance

In the context of human resource management, work motivation is considered an internal force that drives individuals to achieve organizational goals through optimal task execution (Robbins & Judge, 2019). High motivation encourages employees to work harder, be more responsible, and be committed to service quality.

As a mediating variable, work motivation links the influence of discipline and competence on service performance. Disciplined and competent employees will have a stronger drive to provide excellent service to the public. Work motivation, in this case, serves as a psychological mechanism that bridges behavioral and ability factors with performance outcomes (Luthans, 2011). Thus, increased discipline and competence without strong motivation will not result in optimal service performance.

Various studies exploring work motivation as a mediator between work discipline, work competence, and service performance in public services have found a consistent pattern: strong work discipline and high competence do not necessarily result in superior service outcomes; Conversely, both increase employee motivation, which in turn results in higher service performance (Robbins & Judge, 2019; Sutanto & Suwondo, 2018). Discipline contributes by establishing routines, clear expectations, and accountability mechanisms that reduce absenteeism and procedural errors, creating conditions in which motivated employees can apply their skills effectively (Hasibuan, 2019; Rivai & Sagala, 2020). Competence—measured as knowledge, technical skills, and problem-solving abilities—directly equips employees to perform tasks well, but its effect on customer satisfaction and service reliability is significantly amplified when employees are motivated to use and refine these skills (Spencer & Spencer, 1993; Armstrong, 2014).

Quantitative studies using structural equation modeling often report partial or full mediation by motivation, suggesting that much of the impact of competence and discipline on performance flows through increased motivation (Suryani & Putra, 2020; Lestari & Ghozali, 2021). Intervention studies corroborate this: training programs that enhance competency produce greater improvements in service metrics when paired with motivational supports such as goal setting, feedback, and recognition (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Gagné & Deci, 2005).

Meta-analyses synthesize these findings, estimating a combined effect size for the competency-to-motivation-to-performance pathway, with a smaller but significant effect for the discipline-to-motivation-to-performance pathway (Judge et al., 2001; Kim & Park, 2020). Methodological limitations remain, but the practical implications are clear: combine competency development and discipline enhancement systems with interventions that intentionally focus on motivation. In short, interventions that target competency and discipline are most successful when they intentionally foster sustained employee motivation.

Based on this literature review, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H1: Work discipline has a significant effect on service performance.

H2: Work discipline has a significant effect on work motivation.

H3: Work competence has a significant effect on service performance.

H4: Work competence has a significant effect on work motivation.

H5: Work motivation has a significant effect on service performance.

H6: Work discipline has a significant effect on service performance through work motivation.

H7: Work competence has a significant effect on service performance through work motivation.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The population of this study was 73 employees of the Civil Service Police Unit in Mojokerto City, East Java, Indonesia. The sample size was determined using a saturated sampling technique, where the entire population was sampled. The basis for this saturated sampling technique is Arikunto's (2014) opinion that if the number of subjects (population) is less than 100, it is better to sample all of them, thus categorizing the study as a population study.

To obtain relevant and valid data, the data collection method used a questionnaire, distributed to respondents. The instrument was measured using a Likert scale, a psychometric scale commonly used in survey research. Responses to four research variables: work discipline, work competence, service performance, and work motivation, included: strongly agree, agree, somewhat agree, disagree, and strongly disagree.

Next, the data was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) – PLS. The decision to use the SEM PLS data analysis technique is based on the consideration that it does not require normally distributed data, can use a small sample size (recommended minimum of 30), does not require sample randomization, can use a measurement scale other than intervals, can use formative indicators to measure latent variables, is suitable for use as a procedure for developing theory at an early stage, and allows for very complex models with many latent variables and indicators (Ghozali and Latan, 2020).

IV. RESULTS

Outer Model Evaluation

The measurement model demonstrates the relationship between manifest variables or measurement items and the latent variables in the study. These tests include convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability.

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Convergent Validity Test

Convergent validity is determined based on the principle that measures of a construct should have a high correlation. The convergent validity of a construct with its reflective indicators is evaluated using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). According to Ghazali and Latan (2020), the convergent validity test uses a parameter of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.5. The following are the results of the convergent validity test.

Table 1. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	Average variant extracted (AVE)	Decision
Work discipline	0.649	Valid
Work competence	0.664	Valid
Work motivation	0.613	Valid
Service performance	0.664	Valid

Based on Table 1, it is known that the AVE value for each construct is >0.5. Therefore, the convergent validity test results are met because all items in each construct can be declared valid.

Next, we test Convergent Validity using Outer Loading or Factor Loading Values. An indicator is considered to have good Convergent Validity if its Outer Loading value is >0.7. The following are the Outer Loading Values for each indicator in the research variables.

Table 2. Convergent Validity

Variables	Indicator	Outer loading	Decision
Work discipline (X1)	X1.1	0,814	Very Strong
	X1.2	0,835	Very Strong
	X1.3	0,728	Very Strong
	X1.4	0,774	Very Strong
	X1.5	0,868	Very Strong
Work competence (X2)	X2.1	0,753	Very Strong
	X2.2	0,783	Very Strong
	X2.3	0,776	Very Strong
	X2.4	0,818	Very Strong
	X2.5	0,888	Very Strong
	X2.6	0,862	Very Strong
	X2.7	0,816	Very Strong
Work motivation (Y)	Y.1	0,771	Very Strong
	Y.2	0,741	Very Strong
	Y.3	0,751	Very Strong
	Y.4	0,839	Very Strong
	Y.5	0,713	Very Strong
	Y.6	0,858	Very Strong
	Y.7	0,798	Very Strong
Service performance (Z)	Z.1	0,851	Very Strong
	Z.2	0,729	Very Strong
	Z.3	0,834	Very Strong
	Z.4	0,905	Very Strong
	Z.5	0,913	Very Strong
	Z.6	0,906	Very Strong
	Z.7	0,769	Very Strong
	Z.8	0,635	Less Strong
	Z.9	0,745	Very Strong

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Based on Table 2, the results of the convergent validity test indicate that all indicators for each variable have an outer loading value > 0.70 , indicating that each indicator has a very strong correlation with the construct it measures. This indicates that the convergent validity of the model meets the requirements.

Indicator Reliability

To measure the reliability of a construct in SEM-PLS, two methods are used: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. This research instrument is considered reliable if the composite reliability value is > 0.7 and the Cronbach's Alpha value is > 0.7 . The results of the reliability test are presented in the following table.

Table 3. Indicator Reliability

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Work discipline	0.864	0.869
Work competence	0.915	0.918
Work motivation	0.894	0.900
Service performance	0.935	0.940

Table 3 shows that all constructs had Cronbach's Alpha values > 0.70 and Composite Reliability values > 0.70 . According to Ghozali and Latan (2015), a construct or variable is considered reliable if its Cronbach's Alpha value is > 0.70 and its composite reliability value is > 0.7 . The closer the composite reliability value is to 1, the higher the internal consistency reliability (Hair et al., 2022). Therefore, it can be concluded that all research constructs are reliable.

Structural Model Evaluation Results

The structural model evaluation aimed to predict the relationships between latent variables using R-square. R-square values of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 indicated strong, moderate, and weak models, respectively (Chin et al., 1998). The coefficient of determination is a way to assess the extent to which an endogenous construct can be explained by an exogenous construct.

Table 4. Goodness of Fit Test

Variables	R-Square Value
Work motivation	0.721
Service performance	0.641

Based on table 4, the R-Square value for work motivation of 0.721 can be interpreted as meaning that 72.1% of the variation in work motivation can be explained by work discipline and work competence. This value is in the strong category according to Chin's (1998) criteria, indicating that work discipline and employee competence contribute strongly to strengthening work motivation. Furthermore, the R-Square value for service performance of 0.641 means that 64.1% of the variation in service performance can be explained by work discipline, work competence, and work motivation. This value is in the strong category, indicating that these three variables are able to explain more than half of service performance.

Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis testing was conducted to determine the influence of job characteristics and discipline on employee performance, both directly and as moderated by organizational culture. The following table presents the results of the hypothesis testing.

Table 5. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	T statistics	P values	Decision
Work discipline ---> Service performance	1.100	0.052	Rejected
Work discipline ---> Work motivation	2.350	0.019	Accepted
Work competence ---> Service performance	8.954	0.000	Accepted
Work competence ---> Work motivation	4.114	0.000	Accepted
Work motivation ---> Service performance	2.845	0.006	Accepted
Work discipline ---> Work motivation ---> Service performance	2.268	0.020	Accepted
Work competence ---> Work motivation ---> Service performance	2.768	0.007	Accepted

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that the five hypotheses proposed in this study are accepted because the t-statistics are > 1.96 and the p-values are < 0.05 . One hypothesis is rejected because the t-statistics (1.100) are < 1.96 and the p-values (0.052) are > 0.05 .

V. DISCUSSION

The Effect of Work Discipline on Service Performance

The results of the hypothesis testing indicate that work discipline does not significantly influence service performance, as indicated by the t-statistic value of 1.100 and the p-value of 0.052. This confirms that work discipline cannot improve service performance at the Mojokerto City Civil Service Police Unit, East Java, Indonesia. Work discipline does not significantly influence service performance because discipline emphasizes compliance with rules and procedures rather than the quality of interactions and creativity in service delivery. Disciplined employees do not necessarily possess intrinsic motivation or high empathy for the needs of service users (Robbins & Judge, 2019). In the context of public services, performance success is largely determined by factors such as competence, work motivation, and organizational support (Mangkunegara, 2017; Wibowo, 2020). If discipline is rigidly applied without being balanced by motivational encouragement and a service-oriented work culture, employees tend to work merely to fulfill formal obligations, rather than providing the best service. Therefore, discipline alone is not sufficient to significantly improve service performance.

Several studies have shown contradictory findings, stating that work discipline has no significant effect on service performance. Research by Hasibuan (2019) and Rivai (2020) confirms that work discipline actually has a strong and positive influence on improving employee performance, particularly in the public service sector. Work discipline reflects employees' level of compliance, responsibility, and awareness of organizational rules and standards. Highly disciplined employees tend to work more regularly, on time, and adhere to service procedures, thus enabling them to deliver efficient and high-quality work. Furthermore, Simamora's (2018) research also shows that work discipline contributes to increased employee motivation and professionalism in providing public services. Therefore, work discipline remains a crucial element in achieving optimal service performance oriented toward public satisfaction (Hasibuan, 2019; Simamora, 2018; Rivai, 2020).

However, work discipline may not significantly impact service performance because compliance with regulations alone does not always reflect the quality of service provided. In the context of public service organizations, other factors such as work motivation, competence, and organizational culture often play a more dominant role (Robbins & Judge, 2017; Mangkunegara, 2019). Disciplined employees may not necessarily possess a strong sense of service or the interpersonal skills needed to serve the public effectively. Furthermore, a bureaucratic work environment that lacks support for innovation can make work discipline an administrative routine without any real performance improvement (Gibson, Ivancevich, Donnelly, & Konopaske, 2012). Thus, although discipline is important for maintaining order and regularity, its influence on service performance can be weakened when it is not accompanied by intrinsic motivation, inspirational leadership, and a fair reward system (Rivai & Sagala, 2020).

The Influence of Work Discipline on Work Motivation.

The results of the hypothesis test indicate that work discipline significantly influences work motivation, with a T-statistic of 2.350 and a P-value of 0.019. This confirms that strong work discipline can increase the work motivation of employees at the Mojokerto City Civil Service Police Unit, East Java, Indonesia. This finding aligns with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (2017), which states that factors such as responsibility, recognition, and achievement (which are related to discipline) are intrinsic motivators that can increase job satisfaction and morale. Therefore, these results reinforce the view that discipline is not merely a control tool but also an instrument for building employee morale and internal work drive.

This research confirms the existing theoretical foundation and emphasizes the importance of discipline management within the framework of increasing work motivation. In this context, discipline is viewed not only in terms of compliance with regulations but also as a symbol of professional commitment and responsibility (Hasibuan, 2019; Rivai & Sagala, 2020). These findings have a direct impact on human resource management practices in the public sector, particularly in the design of work monitoring and evaluation systems (Mangkunegara, 2017). Implementing discipline based on rewards and coaching, rather than solely punishment, can be an effective strategy for sustainably increasing work motivation (Gibson, Ivancevich, Donnelly, & Konopaske, 2012; Robbins & Judge, 2019).

The Influence of Job Competence on Service Performance.

The results of the hypothesis test indicate that job competence significantly influences service performance, with a T-statistic of 8.954 and a P-value of 0.000. This confirms that high job competence can improve service performance at the Mojokerto City Civil Service Police Unit, East Java, Indonesia. These findings support Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (2017), which states that motivating factors, such as recognition, achievement, and the work itself, have a direct influence on job satisfaction and performance. Furthermore, these results also reinforce the assumptions of Vroom's Expectancy Theory, which states that individuals are motivated to perform optimally when they believe their efforts will result in good performance and be rewarded.

Within a broader theoretical framework, these findings emphasize the importance of psychological aspects in driving the quality of public services. When work motivation is used as an intervening variable, these research findings open up the possibility of developing a new understanding that, in the context of public service organizations, the quality of work outcomes is determined not only by hard skills (technical competence), but also by intrinsic factors such as passion, belonging, and inner satisfaction (Ryan & Deci, 2020; Luthans et al., 2015). These findings encourage the development of new theoretical models that emphasize the importance of a balance between structural and affective aspects in creating optimal service performance (Perry & Vandenabeele,

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2015; Bakker & Demerouti, 2018).

The Influence of Work Competence on Work Motivation.

The results of the hypothesis test indicate that work competence has a positive and significant effect on the work motivation of employees at the Mojokerto City Civil Service Police Unit, East Java, Indonesia, with a t-statistic of 4.114 and a p-value of 0.000. This means that the higher an employee's knowledge, skills, and work attitudes, the greater their work motivation. This finding aligns with Skills Theory (Katz, 1955), which emphasizes the importance of managerial, technical, and conceptual skills for work effectiveness, and Maslow's (1954) theory of needs, which states that self-actualization through mastery of competence is a source of intrinsic motivation.

Theoretically, these results confirm that competence is not only a prerequisite for high performance but also a psychological factor that fosters energy and work enthusiasm. Competence serves as a source of internal motivation, not simply an operational tool. In the context of public organizations, these findings can enrich the development of competency theory by adding a motivational dimension.

Practically, increasing work motivation can be achieved through employee competency development, such as ongoing training, job rotation, mentoring, and performance-based evaluation. In a complex work context like the Civil Service Police Unit, increased competency will strengthen self-confidence and work meaning, thereby boosting intrinsic motivation. This research also supports Kurniawan's (2022) findings at the Bandung City Transportation Agency, which showed that increased competency directly increases employee work motivation.

The Influence of Work Motivation on Service Performance.

The results of the hypothesis test indicate that work motivation has a significant effect on service performance at the Mojokerto City Civil Service Police Unit, East Java, Indonesia, with a t-statistic of 2.845 and a p-value of 0.006. This means that the higher the knowledge, skills, and work attitudes of employees, the greater their work motivation, which in turn improves service performance. These findings emphasize the importance of psychological support and intrinsic motivation in improving the effectiveness of public services, particularly in regional regulation enforcement agencies that demand integrity and high work ethic.

The results of this study support Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (2017), which emphasizes that motivating factors such as recognition, achievement, and responsibility significantly influence performance, as well as Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (2000), which highlights the role of intrinsic motivation in driving proactive behavior. Therefore, this study not only strengthens existing theories but also broadens their application in the context of public organizations. Improved service performance resulting from high work motivation suggests that human resource management needs to place greater emphasis on developing personal motivation rather than structural oversight. Strengthening a work culture that provides meaning and appreciation for tasks is key to leadership in the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP). Consistent with the findings of Putra (2021) and Marlina (2019), work motivation has been shown to be a key variable in improving public service performance in a bureaucratic environment.

The influence of work discipline on service performance Mediated by Work Motivation.

Hypothesis testing results indicate that work motivation significantly mediates the influence of work discipline on service performance at the Mojokerto City Public Order Agency (Satpol PP), East Java, Indonesia, with a t-statistic of 2.268 and a p-value of 0.020. This indicates that work discipline can boost service performance by strengthening work motivation. Work discipline is a form of employee compliance with applicable rules, norms, and operational standards within the organization. Employees with high levels of discipline demonstrate punctuality, responsibility, and consistency in carrying out their duties. Good work discipline creates an orderly work environment, encourages efficiency, and minimizes errors in the public service process (Hasibuan, 2019).

Strong discipline also forms the basis for high work motivation. Employees accustomed to working in a disciplined manner will develop a sense of responsibility and satisfaction with their work results. This fosters intrinsic motivation to continuously improve work quality and contribute more to the organization (Robbins & Judge, 2019). Work motivation is a driving factor linking discipline to improved service performance. When work motivation increases, employees will work with greater enthusiasm, be results-oriented, and strive to provide fast, accurate, and satisfactory service to the public (Mangkunegara, 2020).

Thus, work discipline not only directly impacts service performance but also indirectly through increased work motivation. The higher the level of employee discipline, the greater their motivation to provide quality public services. The combination of discipline and work motivation is key to creating a professional, high-integrity civil service capable of meeting public expectations for the quality of government services (Siagian, 2018).

The Influence of Work Competence on Service Performance Mediated by Work Motivation.

Hypothesis testing results indicate that work motivation significantly mediates the effect of work competence on service performance at the Mojokerto City Civil Service Police Unit, East Java, Indonesia, with a t-statistic of 2.768 and a p-value of 0.007. This indicates that work competence can boost service performance by strengthening work motivation. Work competency is a fundamental factor that directly influences employee service performance, especially when mediated by work motivation. Competence encompasses the set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to effectively perform tasks in accordance with organizational standards (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). Employees with high competency are able to understand work procedures,

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resolve problems quickly, and provide appropriate, friendly, and professional service to the public. Strong competency also reflects an individual's readiness to face work challenges and the ability to adapt to changes in the work environment (Wibowo, 2020).

However, competency alone is insufficient without adequate work motivation. Work motivation acts as an internal driver that encourages employees to optimally apply their competencies to achieve expected performance (Robbins & Judge, 2019). Highly motivated employees demonstrate dedication, responsibility, and strong commitment to their duties, significantly improving service quality (Mangkunegara, 2017). Conversely, high competency without motivation can result in underutilization of work potential.

Thus, work motivation acts as a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between work competency and service performance. The combination of strong competency and high motivation will produce productive, results-oriented employees who are capable of providing fast, accurate, and satisfactory public services in line with community expectations and organizational goals (Hasibuan, 2019).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Successful service performance improvements are determined not only by employee technical skills, but also by strong discipline and internal motivation. Research shows that work discipline has a positive and significant impact on both work motivation and service performance. Employees with high levels of discipline—in terms of punctuality, adherence to regulations, and responsibility for their duties—tend to have better work motivation and provide more optimal service to the public.

Furthermore, work competence has also been shown to significantly influence motivation and service performance. Employees with adequate competence, both in knowledge, skills, and professional attitudes, are able to adapt to job demands and provide quality service. This competence fosters higher self-confidence and job satisfaction, thus positively impacting service performance.

Work motivation in this study acts as a mediating variable, strengthening the relationship between discipline and competence on service performance. This means that when employees possess strong discipline and competence, coupled with high motivation, service performance will significantly improve. Therefore, improving public service performance can be achieved through human resource management strategies that focus on establishing work discipline, developing sustainable competence, and strengthening intrinsic motivation. This finding emphasizes the importance of synergy between individual and organizational factors in creating public services that are effective, responsive, and oriented towards public satisfaction.

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